

An Analysis of Child Psychiatry Consultations in a Training and Research Hospital: A Five-Year Retrospective Study

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Abstract

Objective: Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry (CLP) plays a critical role in supporting the mental health of pediatric patients with physical illnesses and improving medical outcomes. This study aimed to evaluate the profile, reasons for request, and diagnostic distribution of child and adolescent psychiatry consultations in a training and research hospital.

Materials and Methods: All psychiatric consultations requested for children aged 0–18 years between November 2020 and December 2025 were retrospectively reviewed. Data regarding sociodemographic characteristics, requesting units, reasons for consultation, and DSM-5 diagnoses were analyzed. Descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests were used for statistical analysis.

Results: Over a five-year period, out of 1,222,309 pediatric admissions (emergency and inpatient), the overall consultation request rate was 0.024%. Among the 302 consultations, the majority were female (60.26%). The highest request rates originated from the Emergency Department (47.35%) and Pediatrics (42.72%). Suicide attempts and intoxication were the most frequent reasons for request. While 45.4% of cases were identified as true psychiatric emergencies, a strong correlation (84.4%, $p < 0.001$) was observed between the initial referral and final psychiatric assessment.

Conclusion: Consultation request rates were found to be remarkably lower than literature averages and the prevalence of mental disorders in the general population. This suggests a need to increase psychiatric awareness among physicians managing pediatric cases and to strengthen interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure early diagnosis and effective intervention

Keywords: Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry, Child and Adolescent Psychiatry, Psychiatric Emergency, Suicide Attempts, Pediatric Consultation

I. INTRODUCTION

Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry is a growing subspecialty of psychiatry that has existed for over 40 years [1]. It focuses on the intersection between psychiatry and medicine and is practiced across a wide range of clinical settings [2]. Consultation, which simply means "referral," in the pediatric group involves the psychiatric evaluation and treatment of children with physical illnesses by child and adolescent psychiatrists at the request of the child's primary physicians [3].

According to World Health Organization 2025 data, one in seven individuals aged 10-19 worldwide experiences a psychiatric disorder, accounting for 15% of the global burden of disease in this age group [4]. When these children are hospitalized medically, pediatric consultation-liaison psychiatry services can help manage psychiatric conditions and improve medical outcomes [5]. With the rising need for pediatric mental health services globally, the demand for psychiatric consultation for pediatric patients has increased over the last decade [5]. In our country, however, the demand for consultation for pediatric patients remains relatively low [6]. This low demand may be explained by difficulties faced by physicians working with children in recognizing psychiatric disorders and inadequate collaboration between physicians [7].

Psychiatric disorders, particularly anxiety and depression, are more prevalent among hospitalized children compared to the general population [3]. Risk factors for psychiatric disorders in hospitalized children include premorbid psychiatric disorders, parental psychiatric disorders, family relationship problems, chronic illness,

severe diagnoses, frequent hospitalizations, inadequate preparation of the child for medical interventions, and the families' inability to understand the illness [8].

Due to the limited number of child and adolescent psychiatrists and inpatient services, the number of admissions to emergency departments with psychiatric complaints is quite high [9]. Although the reasons for psychiatric consultation in children and adults are generally similar, in some cases an approach appropriate to the child's developmental level may be required [10].

The co-occurrence rate of physical illnesses and psychiatric disorders has been reported to be as high as 40% [10]. The presence of both physical illness and psychiatric disorders may negatively affect the evaluation and treatment processes of children [7].

Psychiatric emergencies, the most critical intervention area of Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry, are situations where symptoms emerging in one or more areas of emotion, thought, and behavior pose a threat to the patient or others, requiring immediate psychiatric assistance[11]. Psychiatric emergencies include suicide, agitation, anxiety, panic attacks, bipolar disorder-mania, psychosis, and alcohol and substance use disorders[12].

It has been stated that through consultation-liaison psychiatry, providing effective and timely psychiatric intervention to patients increases treatment compliance, shortens hospital stays, and yields beneficial results regarding various medical and socioeconomic factors[13]. One of the critical functions of consultation-liaison psychiatry is to enhance the recognition of psychiatric symptoms and awareness of psychiatric disorders among non-psychiatric physicians[13].

Therefore, by retrospectively screening child psychiatry consultations requested for pediatric patients admitted to our hospital over the last five years, this study aims to examine the status of psychiatric diagnosis, determine the reasons for consultation, and measure the awareness of physicians caring for pediatric patients regarding psychiatric emergencies and symptoms.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethics committee approval (Decision No: 2025/01/10/16) and permission from the Provincial Directorate of Health were obtained for our study. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Child psychiatry consultation services in our hospital are provided on-call by all actively working child psychiatry specialists, with a designated consultant specialist constantly in charge. After obtaining the necessary permissions from institutional authorities, child psychiatry consultations requested for all children aged 0-18 who presented to the hospital between November 2020 and December 2025 were retrospectively reviewed through hospital records. One case, involving a patient over 18 years of age for whom an adult psychiatry consultation was requested, was excluded from the study.

Data regarding the sociodemographic characteristics of the children, past psychiatric disorders, medication use, physical illnesses, the departments requesting the consultations, the reasons for the requests, whether a psychiatric emergency was indicated, whether it was an actual psychiatric emergency, psychiatric diagnoses identified upon evaluation, and the psychiatric treatment and follow-up processes were recorded.

The reason for the consultation request was determined by examining the consultation request notes or the psychiatry response notes. Psychiatric diagnoses were established based on clinical interviews and evaluations according to the DSM-5 (The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) classification. A true psychiatric emergency was defined as a condition requiring immediate psychiatric intervention due to risk of harm to self or others, as determined by a child and adolescent psychiatrist based on clinical evaluation.

A. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical methods were used for data analysis. Categorical variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages, while numerical variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation. The relationship between categorical variables was evaluated using the chi-square test of independence, and the strength of associations was assessed using Cramér’s V coefficient.

III. RESULTS

Between November 2020 and December 2025, the number of children aged 0-18 admitted to the emergency department of our hospital was 1,021,682. During the same period, the number of pediatric patients aged 0-18 receiving inpatient treatment was 200,627. As a result of the 5-year screening, the total number of patients for whom a consultation was requested from the Child and Adolescent Psychiatry Department was found to be 302. Of these, 143 were patients referred from the emergency department, and 135 were patients referred from the wards, the majority of which were from pediatrics (85.9%). Consultations were requested for 24 patients from the outpatient clinics. The departments requesting consultations are shown in Table 3. The rate of consultation requests from the emergency department was 0.014%, while the rate of consultation requests from inpatients was found to be 0.067%.

The sample consisted of 60.26% females and 39.74% males. The mean age of the patients was calculated as 13.87, with a standard deviation of 3.63.

75.51% of patients with comorbid neurodevelopmental disorders had previously used psychiatric medication. In the group without comorbid neurodevelopmental disorders, the rate of psychiatric medication use was 21.74%. Overall, it was observed that 30.46% of patients had a history of psychiatric medication use, while 69.54% did not.

TABLE I
 REASONS FOR CONSULTATION

Reasons for Consultation	Frequency(n)	Percent (%)
Agitation	30	9.9
Anxiety	17	5.6
Drug Intoxication	37	12.3
Abuse	6	2.0
Speech Disorder	8	2.6
Conversion	34	11.3
Self-Harm Behavior	9	3.0
Substance Use	6	2.0
Mania or Psychosis	8	2.6
Somatic Complaint	11	3.6
Suicide	88	29.1
Treatment Non-adherence	14	4.6
Sleep Disorder	5	1.7
Other	29	9.6
Total	302	100.0

When analyzing the reasons for consultation requests, the most frequent reasons were identified as suicide (29.1%), drug intoxication (12.3%), conversion (11.3%), and agitation (9.9%). Consultation reasons categorized under 'Other' included injuries, medication side effects, suspected autism, attention deficit, and pre-operative evaluation.

TABLE II
PSYCHIATRIC DIAGNOSES FOLLOWING EVALUATION

Psychiatric Diagnoses	Frequency(n)	Percent (%)
Anxiety Disorders	31	10.3
Major Depressive Disorder	27	8.9
Disruptive Behavior Disorders	12	4.0
Conversion Disorder	10	3.3
Adjustment Disorder	8	2.6
Bipolar Disorder	7	2.3
Intellectual Disability	7	2.3
Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder	5	1.7
Speech Disorders	5	1.7
Sleep Disorders	3	1.0
Substance Use Disorders	2	0.7
Autism Spectrum Disorder	2	0.7
Psychosis Disorders	2	0.7
Factitious Disorder	2	0.7
Delirium	1	0.3
Encopresis	1	0.3
Catatonia	1	0.3
Somatization Disorder	1	0.3
No Psychiatric Diagnosis	175	57.9
Total	302	100.0

Following the assessment of patients for whom consultation was requested, the most frequently identified psychiatric diagnoses were Anxiety Disorder (10.3%), Major Depressive Disorder (8.9%), Disruptive Behavior Disorders (4%), and Conversion Disorder (3.3%). It was observed that 57.9% of the patients requested for consultation were not assigned a psychiatric diagnosis.

TABLE III
 DISTRIBUTION OF DEPARTMENTS REQUESTING CONSULTATION

Requesting Department	Frequency(n)	Percent (%)
Emergency	143	47.35
Pediatrics	129	42.72
Pediatric Surgery	22	7.28
Anesthesia	3	0.99
Forensic Medicine	1	0.33
Neurosurgery	1	0.33
Dermatology	1	0.33
Home Healthcare	1	0.33
Orthopedics	1	0.33
Total	302	100.0

The highest rate of consultation requests belonged to the Emergency Department (47.35%; 143 cases), followed by the Pediatrics department (42.72%; 129 cases). Pediatric Surgery ranked third with 7.28% (22 cases). Consultation requests from other departments were notably low, with each accounting for less than 1% of the total.

TABLE IV
 LIKELIHOOD OF PSYCHIATRIC EMERGENCY AMONG PATIENTS FOR WHOM CONSULTATION WAS REQUESTED

Is It a True Psychiatric Emergency? (%)	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Total (n)
Emergency Department	85 (59.4%)	58 (40.6%)	143
Pediatrics	45 (34.9%)	84 (65.1%)	129
Pediatric Surgery	6 (27.3%)	16 (72.7%)	22
Other Departments	1 (12.5%)	7 (87.5%)	8
Total	137 (45.4%)	165 (54.6%)	302

It was determined that 45.4% of the patients for whom consultation was requested were true psychiatric emergencies. When evaluated according to the requesting departments, 59.4% of the consultations from the Emergency Department were identified as true psychiatric emergencies. In contrast, 34.9% of the consultations requested by the Pediatrics Department were found to be psychiatric emergencies. The rate of true psychiatric emergencies was lower in Pediatric Surgery and other departments.

TABLE V
PROBABILITY OF CONCORDANCE REGARDING PSYCHIATRIC EMERGENCY STATUS

	Did Psychiatric Emergency Status Match? (n)	Did Psychiatric Emergency Status Match? (%)
Yes	255	84,44%
No	47	15,56%
Total	302	100,00%

In the analysis conducted on a total of 302 cases, an 84.4% concordance was observed between the initial designation as a psychiatric emergency and the final assessment.

TABLE VI
ASSOCIATION TABLE FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF PSYCHIATRIC EMERGENCY

Was It Identified as a Psychiatric Emergency?	Was It a True Psychiatric Emergency? Yes	Was It a True Psychiatric Emergency? No	Total
Yes	129	39	168
No	8	126	134
Total	137	165	302

Expected Value	Yes	No
Yes	76,21192053	91,78808
No	60,78807947	73,21192

Analysis (Chi-square Table)	Yes	No
Yes	36,56358893	30,35886
No	45,84091747	38,06185

X ² :	150,8252
V:	0,706697

Cramér's V	Strength of Association
0,00–0,10	Very weak
0,10–0,30	Weak
0,30–0,50	Moderate
> 0,50	Strong

A statistically significant association was found between being identified as a psychiatric emergency at the time of consultation request and being a true psychiatric emergency following psychiatric evaluation (χ^2

= 150.82, $p < 0.001$). The Cramér's V coefficient was 0.71, indicating a strong association between the variables.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, child psychiatry consultations requested by various departments at a Training and Research Hospital between November 2020 and December 2025 were evaluated. A total of 302 child psychiatry consultations were identified over five years. Of these, 143 were from the emergency department, 135 were from inpatient services (85.9% of which were from pediatric wards), and 24 were from outpatient clinics. During the specified time period, consultations were requested from child psychiatry for 0.014% of pediatric patients (aged 0–18 years) presenting to the emergency department, and for 0.067% of pediatric patients followed in inpatient services.

In a study conducted in 2014, it was reported that child and adolescent psychiatry consultations were requested for 0.48% of pediatric patients presenting to the emergency department within one year, and for 3.25% of pediatric patients followed in inpatient services [7]. In a 2017 study examining consultations requested for pediatric patients followed and treated in pediatric wards, it was found that 1.5% of patients were referred to child psychiatry [14]. In a study conducted in 2019 in a province with a sociodemographic profile similar to that of our study sample, it was reported that 0.11% of patients presenting to the emergency department within one year were referred to the psychiatry department [11].

In a study conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic and covering a two-year period, it was reported that 0.03% of pediatric patients followed and treated in the emergency department, 1.67% of pediatric patients followed in inpatient services, 5.6% of pediatric patients followed in the pediatric intensive care unit, and 0.1% of all pediatric patients presenting to the institution were referred to child psychiatry [15]. In a recent study conducted in a city hospital in Türkiye covering a six-month period, it was reported that consultations were requested from child psychiatry for 0.14% of patients presenting to the pediatric emergency department, 2.07% of pediatric patients followed in inpatient services, and 0.016% of patients presenting to the pediatric outpatient clinic [6].

In studies conducted abroad, the rate of child psychiatry consultations has been reported to range between 1% and 14%, while values as high as 66% have also been reported in the literature [16][17]. When compared with the relevant studies in the literature and our study covering the period between November 2020 and December 2025, the number and proportion of child psychiatry consultations requested from emergency departments, inpatient services, and related outpatient clinics were found to be considerably low. Among the possible reasons for this finding are the low level of awareness among physicians from different specialties responsible for the follow-up and treatment of pediatric patients regarding psychiatric symptoms that may be observed in children, and the negative perceptions of patients and their families toward psychiatry and psychology, which may lead them to underreport psychiatric complaints during clinical evaluation and to show insufficient participation in psychiatric assessment [18].

In our study, the mean age of patients for whom child psychiatry consultation was requested was 13.87 years, and 60.26% were female, while 39.74% were male. In a study examining child psychiatry consultations requested from pediatric wards, it was reported that 63.6% of the patients were female and 36.4% were male [14]. In a 2025 study evaluating child psychiatry consultations requested during the pandemic period, it was reported that 66.6% of the patients were female and 33.3% were male [15]. Consistent with the literature, our findings indicate that female patients constitute the majority of cases for whom child psychiatry consultation is requested.

The most common reasons for consultation were suicide attempt (29.1%), drug intoxication (12.3%), conversion symptoms (11.3%), and agitation (9.9%). Anxiety, abuse, speech disorder, self-harming behavior, substance use, mania, psychosis, somatic complaints, treatment non-adherence, and sleep disorders were among the other reasons for consultation.

In a study examining psychiatric emergencies, the most frequent consultation reasons were suicidal/homicidal ideation (21%), aggression (20.7%), anxiety (15.7%), somatic complaints (11%), suicide attempt (8.6%), self-harming behavior (8.1%), and depressed mood (7.6%) [19]. In a 2022 study investigating child psychiatry consultations in inpatient settings, the reasons for consultation were reported as psychiatric evaluation (22.9%), differential diagnosis (11.9%), agitation (11.9%), suicide attempt (10.6%), and depressive symptoms (8.2%) [16].

When our study findings are compared with similar studies in the literature, a high degree of similarity was observed among consultation request reasons.

In our study, when the diagnoses made according to DSM-5 criteria following psychiatric assessment of patients referred to child psychiatry were examined, it was found that no diagnosis was assigned to 57.9% of the patients. The most frequent diagnoses were anxiety disorders (10.3%), major depressive disorder (8.9%), disruptive behavior disorders (4%), conversion disorder (3.3%), adjustment disorder (2.6%), bipolar disorder (2.3%), intellectual disability (2.3%), and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) (1.7%). Other diagnoses included delirium, encopresis, catatonia, substance use disorders, autism spectrum disorder, psychosis, somatic symptom disorder, sleep disorders, and factitious disorder.

In a study examining child psychiatry consultations requested from pediatric inpatients, the reported diagnoses were adjustment disorder (24.8%), depressive disorder (23.8%), intellectual disability (8.2%), and anxiety disorders (6.4%) [20]. In a similar study, the reported diagnoses were adjustment disorder (26%), depressive disorder (13.9%), anxiety disorder (13.9%), cognitive delay (4.6%), and conduct disorder (3.9%) [16]. In a recent study evaluating child psychiatry consultations in a city hospital, post-assessment diagnoses included depressive disorder (13.3%), substance use disorder (9.7%), attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (8.6%), anxiety disorder (7.5%), adjustment disorder (6.2%), and developmental delay (5.2%), while no diagnosis was assigned to 39.3% of patients [6].

The diagnostic distribution observed in our study was found to be consistent with the literature.

The frequency of psychiatric emergencies has been reported to range between 1% and 5% in the international literature [21]. In a meta-analysis examining psychiatric emergencies, 4% of patients presenting to the emergency department were found to have a psychiatric emergency, and 41.9% of these patients had no prior psychiatric admission [22]. In Türkiye, the frequency of psychiatric emergencies has been reported to range between 1% and 3% [23].

The implementation of brief evidence-based interventions for children presenting to the emergency department with psychiatric symptoms may be beneficial in reducing psychiatric symptoms, facilitating follow-up processes, and ensuring safe post-discharge monitoring and treatment [24]. In our study, a significant proportion of patients referred from the emergency department as psychiatric emergencies were found to be true psychiatric emergencies; however, the consultation rates were considerably low when the overall frequency of psychiatric emergencies is considered. This indicates that a substantial proportion of psychiatric emergencies are not recognized in the emergency department and that patients are discharged without child psychiatry evaluation.

Following the evaluation of consultations, 96% of patients were recommended outpatient follow-up, and 2.3% (7 patients) were referred to inpatient child and adolescent psychiatry units for further follow-up and treatment. In addition, pharmacological treatment was initiated or adjusted in 32.78% of patients. The most commonly prescribed medications were selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), antipsychotics, and benzodiazepines. In the literature, reported rates of pharmacological treatment among consulted patients range between 36% and 70.2%, and our findings were found to be consistent with previous studies [14].

There are a limited number of studies in the literature evaluating child psychiatry consultations in clinical settings in the eastern region of Türkiye. This study is considered to make a significant contribution to the literature, as it is one of the rare studies conducted in this region, covers a broad time period by reviewing the last five years, and includes all child psychiatry consultations from emergency departments, inpatient services, and outpatient clinics.

The main limitations of this study include incomplete data regarding psychiatric findings in some patients, particularly those presenting to the emergency department, and the inability to fully identify all patients who required child psychiatry consultation.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in the Training and Research Hospital where this study was conducted in the Southeastern Anatolia region, which receives approximately 200,000 pediatric emergency admissions annually and provides inpatient treatment for approximately 40,000 pediatric patients per year, the child psychiatry consultation rate was found to be 0.014% in the emergency department and 0.067% in inpatient services. These rates are both considerably lower than those reported in the literature and appear to be at concerning levels when the prevalence of psychiatric disorders in the general population is considered.

Early treatment of psychiatric disorders in children may prevent the consolidation of psychopathology and plays a critical role in protecting community mental health. For this reason, it is necessary to prioritize training of all physicians involved in pediatric care regarding the recognition of psychiatric disorders that should be identified at the primary level, and to increase efforts aimed at strengthening interdisciplinary collaboration.

This study aims to encourage the review of services related to the protection of child mental health and the management of psychiatric disorders, and to provide guidance for the improvement of mental health services.

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